

ISic1336

I.Sicily inscription 1336

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140833

1. [— — — — — — — —]
2. [—]ENE [— — — — —]
3. [—] ΪNEΣ[— — — ἐκ τ]-
4. [ῶν] ἰδίων [ἐποίησεν]
5. [τό] πον [ἐ]α [υτῶ]
6. [καὶ τοῖς ἰδίοις].
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492944

EDCS 39101709

PHI 140833

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0516 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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